

Inverse Problem: Differentiable as a Countable Condition

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Abstract

[한국어] 미분 가능 함수에서 인버스 프로블럼(inverse problem)의 관점을 취하면 “셀 수 있음(countable)”의 정의를 효과적으로 도출할 수 있다. 그리고 이를 기반으로 연속일 때 미분이 불가능한 함수의 함수열에는 그 함수열의 개수 만큼 유용한 속성이 있음을 알 수 있다.

[English] Taking inverse problem aspect from condition of differentiable function, then the condition of countable set can be driven usefully. And based on the condition, function series which is continuous but non-differentiable can be considered to have useful properties countable as much as the number of function series.

1 Introduction

This short idea suggests two aspects of ϵ and δ leading to discrete definition of continuous function. All the notations and pre-definitions follow the referenced book[김성기(2011)].

1. Countable condition can be lead from non-differentiable interval driven by ϵ and δ in differentiable function.
2. From upper condition, function series based on continuous function has minimal monoids at least with the number of countable condition driven.

2 Non-differentiable from Differentiable

It is well known that interval given between $\epsilon - \delta$ is consisted with irrationals. With $f : X \rightarrow Y$, $x_0 \in X, y_0 \in Y, \forall \epsilon > 0$:

$$x \in X, 0 < |x - x_0| < \delta \implies |f(x) - y_0| < \epsilon, \exists \delta > 0$$

And for all $x_0 \pm \delta$ and $y_0 \pm \epsilon$ with exclusion of x_0 and y_0 , any number in open interval is known to be irrational.

With upper occasion, any countable set derived from cannot be field with intervals defined with ϵ and δ . But to say ϵ and δ alone, their ordinals are conserved essentially. For ‘R’ used as operator signifying any possible relation between givens¹:

$$\text{ord } \mathbb{N} \equiv \{x | x = 1_\epsilon \cdot n(\forall \epsilon R \forall \delta)\}$$

So to take inverse problem perspective, Any least number defined(ϵ or δ) that converges always takes the condition of non-differentiable as for not being quotient in real number. But with global interval to function, condition of differentiable function fits in. So any global interval fitting the condition of infinite coverings of non-differentiable irrationals with open end consist numbers that can be taken as rational limit. And the series of coverings can be defined as Cantor’s set – set of irrationals.

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¹At least axiom of order is not denied upon ϵ and δ .

3 Monoid: The least Condition in Property

So, with upper occasion, any covering defines each and any rational. And it is also well known that definition of any continuous has following property represented as interval with $f : X \rightarrow Y$, $x_0 \in X$, $\delta > 0$, $\epsilon > 0$ [김성기(2011)]:

$$f(N(x_0, \delta) \cap X) \subset N(f(x_0), \epsilon) \cap Y$$

For each definition of complex monoid, needs a set of single monoids that bring conditions consisting complex monoid. With each unique rational as being considered as conditional monoid, any covering set up a single monoid driven from excluding irrational.

4 Inverse Problem: Conversion of already known to useful property

Driven from Yoneda lemma[Yoneda(1954)], this fits the least condition of extracting monoid. The least condition of property fulfilling itself to be property needs monoid to complete its definition.

In conclusion, with upper occasion to consist upon axiomatic condition, series of function is derived with inclusion or exclusion of monoids. Then what can be driven as property can be set up as a series of function.

References

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